

ISic0827

Oath and letter of a king

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

letter

Material

marble

Object

stele

Editor

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Autopsy

2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in 1749 outside the walls of Siracusa in the lowest part of the ancient quarter of Akradina (presumably not far from the ancient agora)

Coordinates

37.065577, 15.285904

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 4

Physical Description

A thick fragment of a dense grey stone (identified so far as a calcitic stone), broken on all sides. The rear is rough and uneven. The thickness of the stone suggests a substantial free-standing stele, but the unfinished state of the reverse may suggest either that it stood against an existing structure, or that it was not free-standing but built into a monument of some description. The unusual stone has similarities to the material used for the large honorific base for Hieron II, ISic0823

Dimensions

Height 13 cm
Width 36-42 cm
Depth 8 cm

Layout

The text is set out in two columns on the front face. The left margin of the second column is justified, the right margin of the first column is uneven. Part of the text of the right column, from line 6 (the oath) onwards, is indented

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neat and regularly spaced letters (occasionally with a larger space between letters to mark a sense-break).

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

As Dimartino observes (2015: 58-59) it is quite possible that this is a small fragment from a larger dossier of multiple documents; it is also far from certain or necessary that the text in the second column is a direct continuation of the text in the first column (the first has 1st person plural pronouns; the second has a 2nd person plural pronoun; and the text of the oath at column II, line 6 is in turn clearly marked out as a distinct text by indentation, and may not therefore be a direct continuation from the lines preceding - in other words, parts of up to three separate (but related) texts may be preserved here. It seems most likely that the text in column I is part of a royal letter; the text in the first part of column II could be part of the same, or part of a separate letter or decree; the third text is an oath of the boule, which may or may not have been originally included in the preceding document(s).

The form of the letters together with the references in the text to kings (basileis), the Syracusans, and the existence of the city council (boule) all suggest that this text, or dossier of texts, belongs to the reign of Hieron II of Syracuse, most likely in the period between 241 and 215 BC. Although most editors have attempted more or less extensive restoration of the text, as Dimartino argues cogently, there is little sound basis on which to do so: the extent of the missing text before and after is unknown, as is the actual original width of each of the two columns of text. It seems likely that the first column contains a royal letter, perhaps of Hieron II, addressing the Syracusans, and that the overall context is that of consolidating the relationship between the king and the city, with the latter part of column two containing an oath to be sworn by the boule and others, which may form part of that overall process. The stele itself, which might have recorded multiple documents pertaining to this moment, could in turn have formed part of a royal or other public monument in the area of the agora, but this can only be speculation.

Digital identifiers:

TM 285075

EDR 114427

EDCS 14803754

EDCS 39101977

PHI 140297

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